

Management of Agnimandhya in Children by Dietary Regimen

K. Syamily Raj^{1*}, Narayan Pai², Jithesh Chowta³

¹PG Scholar, Department of P.G. Studies in Kaumarabhritya, Alva's Ayurveda Medical College, Moodabidri, Karnataka, India

^{2,3}Associate Professor, Department of P.G. Studies in Kaumarabhritya, Alva's Ayurveda Medical College, Moodabidri, Karnataka, India

Abstract: Agni considered as an important entity in the human body as it is an invariable agent in the process of digestion and assimilation. When there is diminished power of Agni it causes the condition called Agnimandhya. As the seat of Agni is mentioned as the *grahani*, the root cause for most of the *grahani* doshas are Agnimandhya. Children are considered as the most vulnerable population, because they are generally unable to express their problems completely. And they are considered to be having *asampoorna bala*, *sukumara* and *akleshasaha* they are prone to get so many diseases. Agni which plays an important role in children for their health as well as their disease. Improper diet and regimens like faulty dietary habits, pampering child, etc., cause Agnimandhya and which in turn it leads to all other *grahani* doshas such as *ajeerna*, *athisara*, *chardi*, etc. So, for the betterment of child health and there by getting mentally and physically strong kids we can follow some food regimens which maintain a proper Agni and there by cure the Agnimandhya.

Keywords: Agni, Agnimandhya, Dietary Regimens.

1. Introduction

A. Agni

Considered as an important factor in human body, because when *agni* is 'sama' it can make a healthy individual and that person can live in long life, but if it is hampered it cause either disease or else death.¹

B. Grahani

Considered as the *sthana* for *agni* in the body¹.

C. Grahani Doshas

Vikrutha agni create so many diseases those are called *grahini* doshas².

D. Agnimandhya

Among them, *agnimandhya* is considered as important. Because it says *manda agni* can cause so many diseases like *Ajeerna*, *Agnimandhya*, *Vibandha*, etc².

E. Child

Child is considered as most vulnerable population because, they are *sukumaras*, *akleshasaha*, *asampoorna dhathu*, etc so they are mostly affected by fluctuation of *agni*. Which shows marked changes in the growth and development of the child.¹

F. Dietary Regimens

Agni imbalance is mainly caused because of the improper dietary regimens. Mostly in children they are having improper timing of foods, over pampering of the kids, unwholesome food etc can cause improper *agni*, which later develop in to so many other disorders. Same dietary regimens in proper form can prevent and cure the same.

G. Agnimandhya in Children

Arunadatta mentioned the *sthana* of *agni* is between *pakwasaya* and *amasaya* which is considered as the *grahani*.³ *Agni* which is really important in the body which maintain the health also the imbalance of *agni* cause the death of the same.¹ *Agnimandhya* is a condition where *agni* gets vitiated and the power of digestion is impaired. We can correlate it as the loss of appetite. The percentage of healthy children admitted with the complaint of poor appetite is 20-35%⁶. This is mainly because of improper dietary regimen. Food is like a fuel to the body so, in terms of quantity and quality it should be good and proper timing should be managed. otherwise, it causes impairment of *agni*⁶.

2. Materials and Methods

According to the Vaya-awasthas (age patterns) outlined by the acharyas, switching diet might disrupt metabolic processes and cause digestive issues. Agni plays a significant role in this context. Children with weak *agni* suffer from GI disorders, whereas those with excellent *agni* can manage with it.

Foods heavy in sugar, fat, and salt, as well as preservatives and artificial flavouring agents, poor in nutritional value, and low in fibre, are extremely popular among children owing to their taste. Mothers also like ready-to-cook foods as they demand less preparation time. Long-term use of this meal by children with poor physical activity can result in early development of lifestyle problems such as Obesity, Diabetes and dyslipidaemia are two related conditions².

To avoid these diseases and to live healthy life ayurveda recommended certain dietary norms which should be followed by children to become healthy.

A. Dietary Regimens Which Cause the Agnimandhya³

Increased and aggravated doshas, Dhathus and Malas are the

causative factors for all diseases; and their aggravation is caused by indulgence in different unwholesome things (food and regimen) like:

- *Atyambu panath*
- *Vishamasana*
- *Vegadharanth*
- *Swapna viparyath*
- *Baya krodha, etc.*
- *Vyadhita*

Due to excessive consumption of Vata Prakopaka Ahara Vihara, Pitta could not be got proper nourishment of Pitta and contraction of Srotas of Pachaka Pitta occurs. These all phenomenon creates vitiation of Pachaka Pitta, which leads to Agnimandya

B. Dietary Regimens to Follow⁵

Some disorders in children need treatment at the basic (primary) level. Ayurveda, identifies basic herbs formulations and regimens have the potential to treat and prevent diseases at their root cause. These methods and formulations can effectively treat children's GI disorders at the elementary stage.

- Exercise
- Timely intake of food.
- Sleeping on proper time.
- Waking up early morning.
- Eating light food.
- *Laja manda*. (drink prepared from popped cereal)
- Soups
- Buttermilk
- Banana
- Ginger.
- Asafetida
- Leafy vegetables.
- *Padola* (pointed guard), *vasthuka* (*Chenopodium murale*), Radish, Indian gooseberries, etc.
- Fruits Like Pomegranate, Orange, Lemon, Etc.
- Honey, Butter, Ghee, etc.

C. Practical Ways to Increase Kids Appetite

Feeding kids is no less than a challenge for parents, especially during their early years as the body needs ample nourishment and any deficiency in growing years can impact the development of kids. Loss of appetite causes rapid weight loss which ultimately results in developing many health complications for child, so we need to be very careful for improving the appetite of children. Here there are some steps which can increase the appetite.

- Healthy snacks
- Don't force to eat
- Physical activities
- Each meal Time- A Family Time
- No snack in meal time
- NO to TV/Books/Computer/Mobile on a meal time
- Providing structural meal
- Prepare and give meal with seasoning with ginger, pepper, cumin, etc.

- Limited time to complete a meal
- No complaints and scolding in front of food

D. Preparations to Increase Appetite⁹

Ayurveda offers so many preparations for the increase of appetite in children those can be even made in home. Some of those are explaining.

1. *Manda* -1 part of rice and 14 parts of water boiled, filtered and taken the liquid portion along with it *shunti* (ginger) and *saindhava lavan*(Rock salt)
2. *Laaja manda* – Manda prepared with *laja* (popped cereals) added with *dhanyaka* (coariander) and *pippali* (long pepper)
3. *Ushna anna manda* – *hingu* (asafetida) and *sowrchala lavana* (black salt) mixed and taken.
4. *Ghruthayukta yavagu* – 4 *pala* of drug boiled in 64 *pala* of water and reduced to half, thick gruel is prepared good for children who are having weakness and loss of appetite because of a disease.
5. Fine powder of *harithaki* (terminalia chebula) taken along with *shunti* (ginger) or jaggery or *saindhava lavana* (rock salt).
6. *Maricha* (black pepper) powder alone taken with lukewarm water.
7. *Adraka* (ginger) coated with salt, if taken just before a meal its *agni deepana*.

E. Cause of Agnimandhya and it's Remedies¹⁰

The 44th chapter of *Ārogya Rakṣā Kalpadrumaḥ*, a reliable source on Ayurvedic Paediatric Care, discusses *Pratyauśhadha Chikitsa*, which refers to corrective procedures for excessive food consumption. These are the remedies for overeating or dyspepsia induced by specific foods. As home remedies, we can employ these examples in current era.

Table 1

Cause of Agnimandhya	Its Remedies
Fish causes <i>agnimandhya</i>	Buttermilk with <i>lavana</i>
By honey	Water
Rice flour	Hot water
By <i>masha</i> (green gram) <i>mudga</i> (black gram)	Decoction prepared by <i>sunthi</i> and <i>saindhava</i>
By rhizomes (<i>sarva kantheshu</i>)	Powder of <i>hingu</i> and <i>trikatu</i> added with hot water
By Sugarcane (<i>ikshu</i>)	Decoction made up of <i>sunti</i> and <i>mareecha</i>
By <i>Amla dravyas</i>	Powder of <i>viswa</i> and <i>ela</i> added with sugar
By <i>Kashaya dravyas</i>	Powder of <i>yavakshara</i>
By spices	Jaggery added with ghee
By jackfruit	Eat banana

F. Discussion

Agnimandhya considered as the major problem among children. Mandagni (diminished power of digestive fire) causing the stage agnimandhya. This produces so many other diseases all together they can be called as *grahani doshas*. As *grahani* considered as the *sthana* for *agni*, that *agni* when it became irregular or *manda* which in turn produce these *grahani doshas*. In children they are having careless attitude and more pampering from parents cause so many dietary regimen faults.

Agnimandhya is mainly causing because of faulty food regimens can be maintained or cured by proper food regimens. For kids to be away from such regimen we can make some routine life styles and food habits. Simple dietary regimen can cure some of the indigestion problems. Those are also beneficial for kids to fast recovery. By these all we can understand the dietary management in *agnimandhya* is a better option in children.

3. Conclusion

As we stated ill-eating habits in children are mainly due to the impaired/dysfunctioning of Agni. However, Ayurveda has options in solving dysfunctioning agni by providing its beneficiary herbs in the form of daily used formulations to get rid of such GI disorders at primary level. These formulations are easily available and easy to prepare instantaneously. By these measures parents can protect and manage these situations from home itself.

References

- [1] Mohan Das Indolajkil, "Charaka samhitha," chaukamba publication, *chikitsa sthana* chapter-15 sloka -115, 136.
- [2] Arundatta. 21. Vol. 4. Varanasi: Chaukhamba Orientalia; 2000. Vagbhata, Ashtanga Hridaya with the commentaries, Sarvangasundara of Arundatta and Ayurveda Rasayana of Hemadri. edited by Pandit Hari Sadasiva Sastri Paradakara Bhisagacarya. Nidhanasthana:12/1.
- [3] Acharya Vidyadhar Shukla & Ravi Dutt Tripathi, Agnivesha, Charaka Samhita edited with Vaidyamanorama Hindi commentary alongwith special deliberation etc., published by Chaukambha Sanskrit Pratisthan, Reprint year: 2015, Chikitsa sthana, chapter 7/122 sloka.
- [4] charya YT, editor. *Sushruta Samhita of Sushruta, Uttarantra. Ch. 64, Ver. 56*. Varanasi: Chaukhambha Surabharati Prakashan; 2014. p. 812.
- [5] Kaviraja srigovindhadasena virachitha; bhaishajya ratanavali: sidhipradha-hindhi vakyopetha; Sidhinandha Misra; published by chaukambha surabharathi prakashana, Varanasi; Chapter 10; Agnimandhyadi chikitsaparakaranam sloka 4-10,41-45
- [6] https://cms.galenos.com.tr/Uploads/Article_10161/11-16.pdf
- [7] Bhadri Prasad Sav, Krishnadas ayurveda sowraja; Ayurveda padhyapadhy vijana; published by Krishnadas Academy Varanasi, vyadi prakara pathya pathya agnimandhya: page number-244.
- [8] Kanjiv Lochan; dietary rules and prohibitions in different diseases; based on bhaishajya ratnavali; Chapter 5 Agnimandhya (Dyspepsia) page no. 30.
- [9] Sri Srangadhara Acharya praneetha;sharangadhra samhitha:bhaishajya Adhamalla virachitha Deepika deka samanvitha:pandit parasurama satri Vidhya sagara; Gururprasad Sharma: published by chukambha Krishnadas Academy:Varanasi: madhyama khandha: chapter 2 and 3rd page no- 34,45, 56.
- [10] Arogya Rakshakalpadruma; Kerala Traditional Ayurvedic Paediatric Care; Lal Krishna; Banara Ayurveda Series 34; Chowkambha Sanskrit Series Office; Varanasi;1926; Chapter-Pratyoushadha chikitsa page number-203, 204.